

METHOD OF USING ARCHITECTURAL MONUMENTS OF AMIR TEMUR IN TEACHING SUBJECTS ON PAINTING

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Abstract. *The given article presents information regarding the historical content, forms and methods of using architectural monuments of Amir Temur in teaching the subject "Color painting" in specialized educational spheres.*

Keywords: *painting, composition, fine art, work, paint, monument, architectural monument, architecture.*

It is important to suggest that the faculty of fine arts of art educational institutions of Uzbekistan is intended for undergraduate students, for the further development and improvement of students' knowledge in the field of painting, which is considered the leading link in the fundamental science of fine art.

Undoubtedly, the importance of teaching painting is very significant in the professional development of future artists. Another unique feature of this science is that it is aimed at studying architectural monuments and depicting them in paintings. In this regard, it is worth noting that in the direction of theatrical and decorative painting of fine art, the performance of tasks that can be mastered by those studying architectural monuments requires great skills, qualifications and experience from future artists.

Definitely, the choice of topic and work on its content are very important in teaching painting. In this regard, our republic is working to familiarize students with the architectural monuments of the Amir Temur era and their history, to teach them, to develop skills in working with various drawings, and to provide them with comprehensive assistance. Qualified personnel serve in working with these architectural monuments from an expert point of view.

It is known to everyone that Uzbek people have always been creative. Over the years and centuries, their architectural skills developed and became more and more refined. Over time, they built both traditional and unique modern buildings. Historical development quickly changed people, architectural monuments, and eras.

Surprisingly, the Timurid era had a great influence not only on the territory of Turkestan, but also on world civilization. In particular, the architecture of Amir Temur and the Timurid period won high attention not only in the region, but also in the world with its solidity, unique architectural trends, charm and freshness.

Amur Temur ibn Taragai Bahadir was born on April 9, 1336 in the village of Khojalgor, Yakkabog district, today's Kashkadarya region, and this date is noted in history as an auspicious day for the birth of the great Timur dynasty.

It is clear to everyone that Amir Temur and the Timurids made a great contribution to the development of culture not only in Central Asia, but also in the whole world. There is a saying in the Muslim world: "Whoever builds mosques and madrassas will be freed from his sins." Probably, that is why this dynasty, wherever it was, would definitely improve this place (country) and build many buildings, parks, mosques and madrassas, fortresses for the next generation, and also leave

behind unique historical monuments. By the time of the Timurids, architectural, epigraphic, tiled decorations in Arabic Khusnihat script were further improved. Historians - Abdurazzak Samarkandi, Sharofiddin Ali Yazdi, Ibn Ariabshah, Baburiy expressed in their works their personal opinions about the external and internal decoration of the corners of the observatories of Bogi Shamal, Bogi Dilkusho, Bibihanim, Aksaroy, Ulugbek. In particular, the height of the inscription on Bibihanim columns is about 1.5 meters, and, according to Babur, it can be read from a distance of one kurukh (2 km).

The inscription on the facade of Bibihanim - "This world is fleeting, spend it on good" - is also a part of the exterior decoration of the building. These images are often taken from the Koran and Hadith. Usually, poems were written on the walls and dishes of hotels, but it is not surprising that in the 9th and 10th centuries such poems were first used in practical art and gradually moved to the walls.

Unfortunately, due to the policy of disrespect for national values during the former Soviet era, many of them have not been fully preserved to this day, or the existing ones have fallen into ruins. From the first days of independence, serious attention has been paid to this issue in our country. All architectural monuments have been repaired and they tried to restore their original appearance. It should be said that the merits of Timur and many rulers belonging to the Timurid dynasties in the implementation of measures aimed at developing the spiritual worldview of the nation through the construction of such objects as madrassas, mosques, parks, libraries, etc.

Certainly, the creation of famous architectural structures through hard work on cultural life and its development is an integral part of the noble deeds carried out by Amir Temur or the Timurids. They approached Islamic culture with great faith, fought for the prosperity of their nation, independence, the peace of the country, religion. In the cultural heritage of the era of Amir Temur, a special place is occupied by the buildings of mosques and madrassas. The depiction of architectural monuments built during this dynasty in the paintings of artists, seeing them in the brilliance of colors, is important for people to have a complete understanding of these monuments, and it is important that this education is applied in practical activities that meet the requirements of today.

For this reason, it is necessary to give a brief explanation of the historical architectural monuments. Because during the former autocratic regime, not only the era of Timur and the Timurids, but also the history, state, cultural and spiritual level of the monuments they built, the ancestors of our people were humiliated. Cities, like people, have their own destiny and image. Just as members of a large family are similar to each other, so cities of the same country and the same people undoubtedly have similar aspects. The destinies of peoples in the past and current life have created many similarities in the appearance and development of these cities. This similarity is difficult to describe, but it is distinguished by national characteristics and national styles. There are many large and small cities in Uzbekistan. Some of them, like Samarkand, are ancient, and the history of their creation is sung in legends, and some, like the city of Chirchik, are very young, as if they are as old as the independent country itself, since they testify to the flourishing of the country in the East. The masters of our national art did not leave any corner of the monuments without decorations; the heyday of such architectural structures falls on the Middle Ages. Many architectural structures are an example of the harmony of painting and its constructive part. For example, based on the understanding of Islam, inscriptions were used to fully illuminate the meaning that could not be explained by patterns due to the absence of wall painting in the Middle

Ages. It is important to mention the quote, famous phrase of N.V. Gogol: "Architecture enters the language only when it cannot say anything about the people."

Reflecting on the ideological significance of architecture and monumental art, it should be noted that the idea of national independence is active creativity in the formation, revival, repair and popularization of all historical and cultural monuments of our Republic, including those demonstrated by the presence of huge resource reserves in the field of monumental art, architecture and the use of values.

If the main task of wall monumental painting in creating an architectural environment is artistic, then its plot can be used to reflect our history and national culture, solving ideological problems. For example, Ikhshid (ruler) Varhum in Afrosiab had frescoes depicting his life, state, power, international relations and the culture of the kingdom.

Additionally, historical urban development experience, architectural structures, landscapes, even the sun and the sky determine the appearance of the cities and villages of our country. In medieval miniatures, the sky is also depicted in golden color. The word "sunny" country has become an integral part of the word Uzbekistan. There are cities in Uzbekistan, whose ancient monuments reflect centuries of research by folk builders. For example, in the city of Bukhara, which is compared to an open-air museum, the architectural structures of the past are preserved like the apple of an eye. This also determines the basic appearance of new buildings that are built around the monuments in the city. The city of Bukhara is one of the city-museums under the sky, preserving more than a thousand years of history of Central Asian architecture. There are hundreds of ancient architectural structures in the city.

Definitely, historical and cultural monuments built in the last Emirati period, since the time of the Somanites, testify to the fact that magnificent forms of architecture were developing here. The whole world is surprised to see how this process has intensified during the period of Uzbekistan's independence. It is evident that Uzbekistan is taking a leading role in preserving its historical monuments and carefully manifesting them in the development of world culture. In the same way, the city of Samarkand clearly embodies before the eyes the incomparable architectural art of the era of Timur and the Timurids.

It is not a secret that Khiva has preserved the typical appearance of a feudal city built during the last Uzbek khanates. Narrow and crooked streets, chaotic and noisy neighborhoods are brought into a certain order from year to year as a result of new constructions carried out on the basis of redevelopment, but the famous architectural monuments of the past are protected by the state, restored to their original state. This attracts foreign tourists and helps them enjoy this heritage.

The city of Bukhara is called "Bukhara Sharif". Only a small part of the thatched fortress that once surrounded it has survived, but the rare architectural monuments inside Bukhara have mostly survived. Twenty years ago, a garden was laid out on the site of an old cemetery that was in ruins in the city during the Emirate. In this green garden, a tomb of the Somanites stands. This monument, which is a pearl of oriental architecture, is very simple in its structure. It has the shape of a cube with a hemisphere on top. All four sides have the same appearance (base, arch, semicircular arch above the arch, columns at the corners), the architectural decoration is very simple, the interior and exterior of the building are made of bricks of different shapes. The building is surprisingly simple and is an example of architecture before the Arab conquest. At the same time, it reflects the desire of the masters of the 9th-10th centuries to create something new. This building also marked the beginning of the tradition of building dakhma. The experience of building

dakhma in Central Asia has come a long and difficult way and is distinguished by its uniqueness among the peoples of the world. One of the buildings of this category is Chashmayi Ayub Dakhma (1380), which is older in its structure, its conical dome rises above the tall building like a tent. The interior of the dome is decorated with beautiful patterns. Outside the fortress, near the small bluish dakhma of Bayonkuli Khan (1358), the majestic mausoleum of Sheikh Sayfiddin Bokharzi (13th-14th) rises. In the 14th century, a large wooden fence with patterns was made for the sheikh's grave.

The ancient arched fortress, located on the square in the center of Bukhara, has a high and majestic appearance. Under the arch, archaeologists have found many materials dating back to the first years of our era. In the 6th century, the ark was built as a palace and fortress of Sheri Kishvar, the ruler of this land, and until 1920, that is, until the overthrow of the Bukhara Emirate, the ark was a stronghold of the rulers of Bukhara. Palaces, as well as treasury, cabinet, court buildings, dungeons of the last emir had a simple and unique architectural style of construction, and the buildings were surrounded by high, steep walls. Currently, these monuments are part of the Bukhara Museum. The Minaray Tower rises in the city. This strong, high tower consists of belts on all sides. Bricks cut into different shapes created a wonderful, unique landscape. The muezzins' calls to prayer were heard from the sixteen openings of the mezan above the minaret, and guards watched the surroundings of Bukhara from afar.

According to some estimates, there was a suspension bridge between the minaret and the Kalon Mosque. However, in later times, the Kalon Mosque was rebuilt in the early 16th century on the site of the old Jame Mosque in the city. This majestic building with a large stage is surrounded by powerful brick columns and vaulted corridors, between which there are magnificent porches. Opposite the mosque is the Mir Arab Madrasah (1535-1536). These three buildings, built in different periods, together with the minaret form a whole architectural harmony. From the top of the tower, the majestic buildings of the city are clearly visible. Most of the buildings are domed and date back to the 16th century.

In Bukhara, such buildings as the Zargaron Tower, Telfak-Furushan Tower, Sarrofon Tower, and Abdullah Khan Timi are worthy of attention. During the Shaibani period, economic ties between the Russian state and the Central Asian khanates developed, new markets opened, and Central Asia entered the world market.

Commercial buildings in Bukhara, built in the 16th century are distinguished not only by their unique architectural appearance, but also by unique examples of engineering art.

It is important to note that due to the creativity and skill of architects, an ancient domed building arose in Bukhara. Brick and ganch were most often used in architecture. Large mosques-madrasahs of the 16th-17th centuries, for example, named after Abdullah Khan, Kokaldosh, Abdulaziz Khan and other similar buildings, are ancient in their general architectural structure (thick walls, domed pediments, a flower bouquet, towers at the corners). It has a traditional form and impresses with its magnificent appearance and luxury, and the system of closing the roofs of the buildings is convenient, cozy and majestic, and the patterns cause aesthetic pleasure in anyone. At the turn of the XIX and XX centuries, new architectural monuments were created in Bukhara. At the entrance to the madrasah of Khalifa Niyozguli or Chor Minor, a four-domed building was built (1807). Even Sitorai Mokhikhossa, the palace of the last emir, was built in a mixed architectural style, but the interior was decorated with great taste by Bukhara masters. Among these masters was the famous Master Shirin Murodov.

During the years of Uzbekistan's independence, large-scale improvement and construction works have been carried out in the city. Green gardens were created and many new buildings were built instead of narrow and cramped houses. Among these buildings are the Pedagogical Institute, the building of the regional executive committee, the drama theater, the school, the kindergarten and residential buildings. Clean water now flows into and out of the stagnant ponds, which were neglected in the last century. The tourist city of Samarkand, which has preserved many unique architectural monuments, is undergoing reconstruction and new construction. Samarkand is a city with a worthy past, a happy present and an eternal future. Amir Temur is a man who made an incomparable contribution to this universal glory, the emergence of incomparable prosperity, the glorious history of Samarkand. In the first half of the 13th century, Samarkand fell into disrepair due to the oppression of invaders, and castles, mosques and madrassas were abandoned.

According to an Arab tourist who came to our country at that time, Samarkand was so devastated that only a quarter of its former inhabitants remained, architectural monuments were destroyed, ditches were filled in, the city was left without water, and parks dried up. Khatoo recalled that it was impossible to imagine that people would live in this area.

At present time this city is recognized as a real museum under the sky, it is the most convenient city for tourism. There are many higher and secondary specialized educational institutions, cinemas, sewing, textile factories, auto parts factories, several canning and superphosphate plants. Theaters, clubs, wonderful parks and avenues were also built. Already in the Middle Ages, the city went down in history under such names as "Pearl of the East", "Rome of the East", "Poland of the Earth". Twenty-three centuries ago (in 329 BC), the city was named Marokanda after the place where the troops of Alexander the Great attacked it. At that time it was considered one of the major cities of the Sughds. Samarkand, whose 2250th anniversary was celebrated internationally in 2009, has a rich and legendary history.

The hill of Afrosiab, abandoned and ruined, is the ancient site of Samarkand. This city flourished in the Middle Ages. After the Mongol attack in the 13th century, it was deserted for a while. At that time, the Arzis aqueduct, which supplied the city with water, was demolished. After that, life developed outside Africa. On its eastern slope, one after another, the monumental complex of Shahi Zinda began to be erected. It is said that Shahi Zinda appears in more and more new scenes from every angle. In the 14th and 15th centuries, the style of building miraculous dams, built at an angle on the slope of the hill, was often transferred to individually built mausoleums. These mausoleums are located next to the abstract tomb of Kusam ibn Abbas, one of the companions who fought for Islam. In addition to the mausoleums of the emirs, queens and sheikhs of Islam, the Shahi-Zinda complex also has a small mosque-madrasah, where funerals are held, distinguished by their elegance and similar to the tile patterns on their surface. Here, the art of architecture seems to compete with the art of pottery.

However, since the master builder was also a tiler, it can be seen that there is no competition between the art of construction and the craft of painting and laying tiles. Among the tile patterns, the names of some medieval masters are recorded. A master named Fakhri Ali participated in the construction of the Khoja Ahmed mausoleum. Boriddin and Shamsiddin from Samarkand, Zayniddin from Bukhara built the mausoleum of Turkan Ako, which is one of the majestic tombs in Shahi-Zinda, and Ali from Nasaf (Karshi) completed the construction of an unknown mausoleum in the middle.

After the victorious campaigns of Amir Temur in the Western countries, among the Central Asian masters there were also masters brought from Iran. For example, Sheikh Muhammad ibn Khodjabek, a master tile-maker from Tabriz, is mentioned. This master decorated the top of the third hall of the complex with tile patterns. Passing through this alley, he enters the Shahi Zinda mausoleum. Amir Temur is known throughout the Eastern world as the "Dome of Science and Ethical Culture". Through the efforts of Amir Temur and his associates, madrassas, mosques, houses, palaces, bazaars, bridges, roads, stations, baths, canals were built. Descendants, castles and a number of other buildings and structures are countless. The Bibihanim Jame Mosque, built under the direct supervision of Amir Temur, Gori Amir and Ahmed Yasawi, the Zangi Ata mausoleums, the architectural wonders of Aksaroy and Shahi Zindad, the Chinar Garden, the Dilkusho Garden, the Behisht Garden. These include dozens of beautiful palaces and other buildings. These monuments are undoubtedly wonderful examples of human thinking and intellect. According to historian Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi, Amir Temur "did not want to lose an inch of land suitable for construction."

During the reign of Amir Temur (1370-1405), Samarkand became the center of a large state that included all the countries of the Middle East, and many majestic and beautiful buildings were built. The Bibihanim Mosque (1399-1404), which has survived to this day in ruins, still amazes people with its size and magnificence, the variety of patterns. The Mausoleum of Amir Temur (1403-1404), known as Gori Amir, will make a wonderful impression on anyone with its attractive appearance and architectural structure. This is one of the masterpieces of world architecture, which was repaired over the next ten years. This memorial mausoleum is among the most famous mausoleums in the East due to its majestic simplicity and sophistication of architectural forms. From the first half of the 15th century, construction work was developed by Mirzo Ulugbek, the famous grandson of Amir Temur. This ruler left his name in the history of world science, especially for his work in the field of astronomy. The remains of the observatory he built are preserved in one corner of Samarkand, that is, on the Poi-Rasad hill. In the 15th century, this observatory was famous throughout the world, but during the interwars it was damaged and turned into ruins.

The remains of the observatory were discovered by archaeologist V. Vyatkin in 1908-1909 and repaired during the years of Independence. Around the Registan, located in the central part of the city, Mirzo Ulugbek built several monumental buildings. Of these, only one madrasah (1417-1420) has survived, in which not only religious but also secular sciences were taught. The exact dimensions and sizes of the parts of the building, the facade, the corner towers, the beautiful design of the arches of the courtyard, the variety of decor show it as a classic example of medieval monumental architecture. Bricks of different shapes, mysterious ceramics and carved marble stones combine with each other, creating a colorful and charming look. Great changes took place in the Registan in the 17th century. At this time, Yalangtush Bokhodir built the Sherdar Madrasah (1619-1636) in front of the Ulugbek Madrasah, and the Tillakori Madrasah (1646-47-1660) was built on the northern side of the square. Thus, the complex of unique, majestic buildings of Registan was created. Centuries have passed, but the majestic architectural tradition of the Middle Ages, which dominated this land, has been preserved in Central Asia and continues along with modern views.

The city of Khiva, whose 2500th anniversary was celebrated internationally in 1997, preserved such traditions until the last Middle Ages. The city of Khiva consists of a complex of

buildings demonstrating the unique crafts of the masters of ancient times. Conical triple minarets (in particular, the minarets of the Polvankori, Sayidboy, Juma, Kokminor mosques are located in one line and are all higher than each other, the pediments of the madrasah - the largest of them are in the Shergazi-khan Ollokulikhan, Kutlimurad Inak, Muhammad Rahimkhan madrasah), the city is characterized by domes, castle gates, fortress walls and fortifications. In the 18th century, Central Asia lagged behind the general development due to the political and economic stagnation it experienced, although the secrets of preparation were forgotten, but the general principles of monumental architecture were preserved. The peculiarities of the development of Khorezm architecture are known as follows: in the past, as monumental architecture rose, it was influenced by the flood of the era, since in the strict and harsh conditions of the medieval period, obstacles to free creative activity increased.

The Mausoleum of Pahlavon Mahmud (1835) in the architecture of the Khiva Khanate, its size and variety of patterned flowers placed on a blue and white color scheme, leave a great impression. The patterns were created by a Khiva master named Abdullajan with his "magic" art.

The Khan's Palace, the observation hall, the stone courtyard (1832-1841) and other buildings, located inside the fortress demonstrate the unique development of various forms of residential architecture in Khiva. However, their distinctive feature is that most of the buildings are large and decorated. In the architecture of Khiva, blue and white colors received priority. The Islamkhodja Tower (1908-1910) is compared to the symbol of Khiva architecture.

Tashkent, the capital of our country, an ancient and ever-popular city, celebrated its 2,200th anniversary in 2009. This city, which is one of the oldest settlements in Uzbekistan, was firstly mentioned under the name Tashkent in Chinese chronicles of the 1st and 2nd centuries AD, as well as in the works of Yuni, Abu Rayhan Beruni and Mahmud Kashgari, and was among the cities of Central Asia in the Middle Ages held a significant position. However, Tashkent was the political and economic center of Turkestan, which became a royal colony in the second half of the 19th century.

During the years of independence, Tashkent Shark Mashali (the center of cotton growing in the center of one of the independent republics) was again appreciated as a city with developed industry, vibrant culture, tall and unique buildings.

The ancient past of the city left its mark on the winding streets. However, as a result of planning work, it has changed radically, the streets have widened. Although the winding streets of the former "old town" have been preserved, as a result of planned large-scale development, plots, elegant buildings and residential buildings are appearing, and the streets are becoming more beautiful, immersed in greenery.

One of the important tasks of the creative team of architects of the republic is to search for and identify national features in architecture, implement the architectural traditions of Uzbek people. These traditions must be radically changed on the basis of new ideological tasks and the latest design technologies. For example, this is very important for the conditions of the southern part of the country, where the air is hot and very hot. Local experience uses centuries-old technologies and the elegant properties of brick and ganch. Patterns carved on wood and stone, previously used rich ornamental systems, are enriched with new ornamental decorations, for example, various forms on the theme of a bush. It is also filled with images that Islam rejects as makruh.

By summerising it should be suggested that one of the principles of creative use of architectural heritage in solving modern problems is the structural connection of water and greenery. Residential buildings located on Navoi Street, Beruni Square and on the river bank, Uzbek National Drama Theater, a complex of airport buildings and, in particular, State Opera and Ballet Theater named after Navoi are unique features of the memory of Tashkent. The building of Alisher Navoi Theater, created as a result of the creative collaboration of the architect A.V. Shchusev, artist Ch. Akhmarov, Uzbek folk artists Shirin Murodov, Kuli Dzhililov, Aslonkul Tashpolatov, Abdulla Boltayev, Jamal and Bolty Dzhoraev, is a masterpiece of its own image, elegant patterns, the master's skill in working with premises will certainly charm people.

REFERENCES

1. Khudoyberganov R.A. Fundamentals of color science. Publishing house of literature and art named after G. Gulam in 2006.
2. Tashmuradov T. Chizmatasvir. T. Edition of 2012
3. History of the period of Temur and Ulugbek. - T., 1996.
4. Culture and art during the times of Amir Temur and the Timurids. - T., 1996.
5. Akhmedov B. Remembering Amir Temur. T., "Uzbekistan" Publishing House, 1996.
6. Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi. Ancestors of Amir Temur. From the work "Zafarnama". T., General editorial office "Komuslar", 1992.
7. International Amir Temur Foundation "Temur tuzuklari" Publishing and Printing Joint-Stock Company "Sharq". Shot in the head. Tashkent-2002.